

Free Particle Stationary Action Solutions Linked to Zero/Nonzero Rest Mass Waves And Special Relativity

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In classical physics it is well known that a stationary solution of the classical action Integral $\int dt L$, where L is the Lagrangian, leads to a differential equation whose solution $x(t)$ describes classical mechanical motion. In previous notes we have argued that two free particle flow/flux equations $d/dx \text{ partial } A(x,t) = p$ and $d/dt \text{ partial } A(x,t) = -E$ lead to $A(x,t)$ being the classical free particle action with a solution: $A(x,t) = -Et + px$.

In this note, we consider two stationary solutions i.e. $dA=0$ which differ from the classical approach. One is for a particle with rest mass for which we assume $p=E(v)v$. The stationary behaviour leads to the form (Lorentz matrix) of special relativity and also to relativistic/nonrelativistic quantum mechanics for a free particle. The second $dA=0$ solution leads to a zero rest mass particle for which the Lorentz transformation of the first $dA=0$ solution also holds because (x,t) transforms in the same manner for both zero and nonzero rest masses. We argue that $dA=0$ i.e. the action is stationary because $A = -Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant i.e. a dot product.

Flux/Flow Equations and Nonzero Rest Mass

We have suggested in previous notes that one may describe free particle motion by two flux/flow equations:

$$d/dx \text{ partial } A(x,t) = p \quad ((1a)) \text{ and } d/dt \text{ partial } A(x,t) = -E \quad ((1b))$$

$A(x,t)$ is an unknown function in x and t with a solution of:

$$A(x,t) = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

One may immediately note that ((2)) is a Lorentz invariant, but let us assume for the time being that this is not known. For a free particle with rest mass in the relativistic case:

$$A = -t m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv} + xv / \sqrt{1-vv} = -t m_0 \sqrt{1-vv} \quad (c=1) \text{ if } v=x/t \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is the free particle relativistic action whose stationary solution should yield classical mechanical motion.

In this note we argue that there are two other stationary A approaches which yield the form of special relativity, relativistic/nonrelativistic quantum mechanics for a free particle and describe a wave with zero rest mass. (The relativistic/nonrelativistic quantum free particle case is a "wave" for a particle with rest mass. The relationship between E and p differs for the two.)

For the case of a particle with rest mass, we assume that:

$$p = E(v) v \quad ((5))$$

and consider the stationary condition:

$$dA = dE/dv dv (-t) + dp/dv dv x = 0 \quad ((6))$$

To see this in more detail consider beginning with $(0, m_0)$ and $(0,0) = (x,t)$. Then

$$A = -m_0 t \quad \text{and} \quad dA = ((6)) - E dt + p dx \quad \text{but} \quad p = Ev \quad \text{and assuming that} \quad dx/dt = v \quad \text{one finds}$$

$$dA = ((6))$$

$$\text{From } ((5)) \text{ and } ((6)) \quad dE/dv (-t) + E x + xv dE/dv = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Using $v = x/t$ a solution which is consistent with $dx/dt = v$ if one starts with $(0,0) = (x,t)$ initial, one has:

$$(-1/v + v) dvE/E = 1 \quad \text{which yields the solution:}$$

$$E = m_0 / \sqrt{1 - vv} \quad (c=1) \quad \text{and} \quad p = Ev \quad ((8))$$

This is equivalent to a 2x2 unitary transformation of (p,E) using $pp-EE$ as the dot product rule of:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1/\sqrt{1-vv} & -v/\sqrt{1-vv} \\ -v/\sqrt{1-vv} & 1/\sqrt{1-vv} \end{vmatrix} \quad ((9))$$

If (x,t) transforms in the same manner, then $A(x,t) = -Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant. I.e. an invariant under $((9))$.

Zero Rest Mass Case

There is a second stationary solution for $A = -Et + px$ namely:

$$dA = -E dt + p dx = 0 \quad ((10))$$

This holds if $E/p = \text{constant velocity} = c$ for example i.e.

$$-dE t + dp x = dE(-t + cx) \quad \text{with} \quad x/t = c$$

which is an unusual result because it means that this new object's speed is frame independent.

In such a case instead of $p = Ev$ one has:

$$\text{Constant velocity} = E/p \quad ((11))$$

This does not necessarily mean, however, that E and p have the same value as viewed from different frames moving with velocities v relative to a lab frame. It just means that the ratio E/p must stay the same. This is satisfied for the transformation ((9)). ((11)) shows that as $p \rightarrow 0$ i.e. there is very little flow, $E \rightarrow 0$ i.e. there is very little energy so this suggests zero rest mass. ((11)) is the condition of a classical wave (e.g. a photon from Maxwell's em equations, or a wave or a sound wave, although E is written as w (angular frequency) and p as constant/wavelength).

Consider $A = -Et + px$ for a zero rest mass particle.

$$E = pc \quad \text{so} \quad A = E(-t + x/c) \quad \text{If one chooses } t \text{ and } x \text{ such that } A \text{ is zero, then } x/t = c$$

Transforming using ((9)) i.e. viewing from a different frame moving with velocity v relative to the lab frame one has $E' = p'c$ again and A should still be zero.

$$A = 0 = E'(-t' + x'/c) \quad \text{where } x'/t' = c \text{ and } x' = Gx - vGt, \quad t' = -vGx + Gt \quad \text{where } G = 1/\sqrt{1-vv}$$

Setting $c=1$ leads to $A=0$ again.

A general transformation with v in ((9)), however, will transform $(p, E) = (Ec, E)$ of the rest mass zero particle e.g. photon i.e. one has the relativistic Doppler shift.

Stationary Solution and Special Relativistic Invariance

It appears that the stationary feature $dA=0$ of the solution of the flow flux equations (i.e. the classical action for a free particle) is nothing more than the fact that $A = -Et + px$ is an invariant i.e. does not change with changing frames. Thus the root of the stationary behaviour of A for the two new solutions appears to be the idea of a Lorentz invariant dot product.

Conclusion

We consider two free particle flow/flux equations $d/dx \text{ partial } A(x,t) = p$ and $d/dt \text{ partial } = -E$ for which one has the solution $A = -Et + px$. For a free relativistic particle this definition of A is equivalent to the classical action $-t m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$). A main feature of the action in classical mechanics is that it is stationary for the classical solution. No reason is given for this. In this note we seek solutions which keep $-Et + px$ stationary and find two different cases.

The first assumes that $p = E(v)v$ and uses $dA = -dE t + dp x$ where $dE = dE/dv$, $dp = dp/dv$ and $x/t = v$. This is linked to a particle with rest mass from $p = Ev$ which is assumed if one considers a particle with rest mass which is accelerated. Using these assumptions one obtains a differential equation for dE/dv and finds that $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$. This leads to a transformation matrix ((9)) the Lorentz matrix for (p, E) . Given that one uses $dA=0$, one expects (x, t) to transform the same way, thus one has a Lorentz invariant dot product $-Et + px$. This approach pertains to both relativistic and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics for a free particle because one uses derivatives d/dx

partial and d/dt partial to find p and E . Creating an eigenvalue equation i.e. $-id/dx \text{ partial exp}(iA) = p \text{ exp}(iA)$ and $id/dt \text{ partial exp}(iA) = E \text{ exp}(iA)$ yields quantum results. Linking with $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$ yields the Klein-Gordon equation.

A second stationary solution is consistent with constant velocity e.g. $ct = E/p$ which is the relationship for a classical wave if E is like frequency and p like $1/\text{wavelength}$. This holds for light or sound and one may see that $E = pv$ goes to 0 as $v \rightarrow 0$ so there is no rest mass. This leads to an unusual particle whose constant velocity E/p does not change as viewed under the Lorentz transformation ((9)) i.e from different moving frames with velocities v even though E and p change i.e. $E = \gamma pc$ and $E' = \gamma' p' c$. This type of solution, however, keeps A constant i.e. $dA = 0$ because A is a Lorentz dot product. Thus the idea of a stationary classical free particle action is due to the Lorentz dot product being invariant and both free particle quantum mechanics and classical waves follow from $dA = 0$ or solutions which keep A constant.